

EXPLORING LANGUAGE CHANGE COMPUTATIONALLY: LESSONS FROM INTERDISCIPLINARY COLLABORATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Advanced computational methods allow us to analyse vast datasets and uncover previously inaccessible patterns. However, few natural language processing algorithms properly account for the dynamic nature of language, particularly its semantics, which is crucial to humanistic inquiry. Efforts are underway to improve AI systems' understanding of historical context and language dynamics, such as in the automatic detection of semantic change, but human annotation and interpretation is still needed to capture the nuances of language and its cultural context. In this talk I will report on a collaborative project involving digital humanists, computational linguists, software engineers and library curators to analyse the effects of mechanisation on the English language of the nineteenth century. I will discuss the challenges and insights gained from combining voluntary crowdsourcing for historical language annotation with algorithms and design experiments. Integrating these approaches allows us to reach a nuanced understanding of language evolution in response to mechanization and, more broadly, contribute to interdisciplinary research at the intersection of AI and the humanities.

BIO

Barbara McGillivray is a lecturer in digital humanities and cultural computation in the Department of Digital Humanities at King's College London and a Turing fellow at the Alan Turing Institute. She is the editor-in-chief of the *Journal of Open Humanities Data* and the convenor of the MA programme Digital Humanities at King's. She also serves as the president of the ACL Special Interest Group on Language Technologies for the Socio-Economic Sciences and Humanities, as well as the convenor of the Turing special interest group Humanities and Data Science. Her research focuses on computational methods for studying language change in both historical languages and

contemporary data. She has been a co-investigator of the Living with Machines project, a large collaboration between the Alan Turing Institute and the British Library, aimed at investigating the effects of mechanization through the analysis of British historical newspaper collections. Her most recent book is *Applying Language Technology in Humanities Research: Design, Application, and the Underlying Logic* (co-authored with Gábor Mihály Tóth, Palgrave Macmillan, 2020).

IZVLEČEK PREDAVANJA

Napredne računalniške metode nam omogočajo analizo ogromnih količin podatkov in odkrivanje prej nezaznavnih vzorcev. Le malo algoritmov za obdelavo jezika pa ustrezno upošteva dinamično naravo jezika, predvsem semantiko, ki je ključna za humanistične raziskave. Potekajo prizadevanja, da bi sistemi umetne inteligence bolje razumeli zgodovinski kontekst in dinamiko jezika, na primer pri samodejnem zaznavanju semantičnih premikov, vendar za zaznavanje finih odtenkov jezika in kulturnega konteksta še vedno potrebujemo človeško označevanje in interpretacijo. Na predavanju bom poročala o interdisciplinarnem projektu, v katerem smo za analizo učinkov mehanizacije na razvoj angleškega jezika v 19. stoletju sodelovali digitalni humanisti, računalniški jezikoslovci, programerji in knjižničarji. Razpravljala bom o izzivih in spoznanjih, ki jih je prineslo združevanje množičenja za označevanje zgodovinskega jezika, algoritmov in oblikovalskih eksperimentov. Integracija omenjenih pristopov nam namreč omogoča večplastno razumevanje evolucije jezika ob prihodu mehanizacije ter v širšem prispeva k interdisciplinarnim raziskavam na stičišču umetne inteligence in humanističnih ved.

O PREDAVATELJICI

Barbara McGillivray is predavateljica digitalne humanistike in računalniške kulturologije na oddelku za digitalno humanistiko King's College London in raziskovalka na inštitutu Alan Turing. Je glavna urednica revije *Journal of Open Humanities Data*, koordinatorka magistrskega programa Digitalna humanistika na King's College London, predsednica posebne interesne skupine za jezikovne tehnologije za socio-ekonomske vede in humanistiko pri združenju ACL ter koordinatorka posebne interesne skupine Humanistika in podatkovna znanost na inštitutu Alan Turing. Njene raziskave se osredotočajo na računalniške metode za raziskovanje jezikovnih sprememb tako v

zgodovinskem jeziku kot v sodobnih podatkih. Bila je med glavnimi raziskovalci projekta *Living with Machines* (Živeti s stroji), obsežnega sodelovanja med inštitutom Alan Turing in narodno knjižnico British Library, pri katerem so skozi analizo britanskih zbirk zgodovinskega časopisja raziskovali učinke mehanizacije. Njena najnovejša knjiga je *Applying Language Technology in Humanities Research. Design, Application, and the Underlying Logic* (soavtor Gábor Mihály Tóth, Palgrave Macmillan 2020).